

ADMINISTRATIVE INFORMATION**1 Title**

1.1 Identification: Panagenesis of the paranasal sinuses detected through medical imaging – a systematic review protocol

1.2 Update: Not applicable

2 Registration

2.1 To be registered in The International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO).

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3.2 Contributions:

(1) Conception or design; (2) data acquisition, analysis or interpretation; (3) intellectual content development or critical review; (4) final version approval; and (5) research integrity.

AHMO: 1 – concept, 2 – data acquisition and interpretation, 3 – intellectual content development, 4 – final version approval and 5 – research integrity.

ABSO: 1 – design, 2 – data interpretation, 3 – critical review, 4 – final version approval and 5 – research integrity.

APFMG: 1 – design, 2 – data interpretation, 3 – intellectual content development, 4 – final version approval and 5 – research integrity.

CAS and CMSVN: 1 – design, 2 – data analysis, 3 – critical review, 4 – final version approval and 5 – research integrity

RS and AF: 1 – concept and design, 2 – data acquisition and interpretation, 3 – intellectual content development and critical review, 4 – final version approval and 5 – research integrity

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INTRODUCTION

6 Rationale: Introduction

The human paranasal sinuses are air-filled cavities in pneumatic bones that can be visualized through medical imaging [1]. They are located in the frontal, maxillary, ethmoid and sphenoid bones, and are distributed bilaterally in the viscerocranium [2]. Their clinical relevance is mainly related to the fields and procedures within otolaryngology, allergology and maxillofacial surgery [3]. In parallel, other applications are described in scientific literature, such as those related to human identification and forensic anthropology [4].

Anatomic variations can occur in the paranasal sinuses [5]. They can be more common such as pneumatization with alveolar extensions of the maxillary sinuses, deviated intersinus septum of the frontal sinuses, hypoplasia and hyperplasia. Other variations can be rare such as sinusal agenesis [5]. The scientific literature has described prevalence rates of paranasal sinus agenesis for specific sinus types [5], but part of it has dedicated their attention to an even more uncommon entity: the total agenesis of paranasal sinuses (also referred to as panagenesis) [6-15]. This condition is described as the lack of developed and,

consequently, pneumatization of the frontal, maxillary, ethmoid and sphenoid bones, and has been reported to be accompanied by symptoms such as nose stuffiness and facial fullness [14,15]. Despite the symptoms, clearly association with clinically visible signs are scarce or null [15].

A common medical image approach to visualize and register anatomic variations and pathological conditions of the paranasal sinuses has been computed tomography [16], which yields multiplanar navigation in axial, coronal and sagittal views through a realistic assessment of the maxillofacial anatomy and its anatomic variations [17]. Other approaches include the combined radiographic assessment of the skull with plain radiographic projections in frontal and lateral aspect [6].

Understanding the case-specific characteristics of the panagenesis of the paranasal sinuses in adolescents and adults, their imaginological representation and patient's signs and symptoms is fundamental to be more prepared for assertive clinical diagnosis and treatment of these patients. In parallel, other fields, such as those forensic-related, can also benefit from investigating this condition, since occurrence in practice is normally unanticipated.

In this context, the present systematic literature review aimed to revisit cases that have been reported regarding the presence and radiographic registration of the panagenesis of the paranasal sinuses in adolescents and adult individuals.

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7 Objectives: This study aimed to investigate the case-specific characteristics of adolescents and adult individuals (P) with panagenesis of the paranasal sinuses (Co) through medical imaging (Co).

Population (Pop) standing for adolescents and adult individuals, Condition (Co) for panagenesis of the paranasal sinuses and Context (Co) for medical imaging detection.

METHODS

8 Eligibility criteria

- The inclusion criteria consist of studies that have applied medical imaging detection methods for the visualization of the agenesis of paranasal sinuses, and that have reported case-specific characteristics of each individual, such as sex, age and systemic condition.

- The exclusion criteria consist of studies that reported the condition for children, that are not designed observational descriptive such as case reports and case series. Excluded study designs will be experimental studies, observational analytical, and letters to the editor, editorials, book, book chapters, abstracts published in annals of conferences, regulatory documents, legislation and protocols, and studies with secondary data, namely literature reviews. Restrictions of language, year and status of publication will not be applied.

9 Information sources

Primary data will be searched in the following sources: Medline via PubMed (<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>), LILACS (<https://lilacs.bvsalud.org/>), Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com/>), SciELO (<https://www.scielo.br/>) and Web of Science (<https://www.webofscience.com/>). To avoid selection bias, grey literature will be retrieved in part from Open Access Theses and Dissertations (OATD: <https://oatd.org/>) and Open Grey via Dans EASY (<https://easy.dans.knaw.nl/ui/datasets/id/easy-dataset:200362/tab/2>)

10 Search strategy

To guide the search, the following question will be considered: “*What are the case-specific characteristics of adolescents and adult individuals with panagenesis of the paranasal sinuses detected though medical imaging?*”

The question considers the acronym CoCoPop, in which Co (condition) stands for panagenesis of the paranasal sinuses, Co (context) stands for the detection of the condition through medical imaging and Pop (population) stands for adolescents and adult individuals.

The search strategy will be constructed based on Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) compatible with PubMed's search engine, Descriptors in Health Sciences (DeCS) for LILACS and free terms. Boolean operators "AND" and "OR" will be used to combine the terms forming comprehensive search strings tailored for each database. Three blocks of terms will be considered: the first for anatomy-related terms (e.g. sinus, sinuses, paranasal), the second for condition-related terms (e.g. agenesis, aplasia, panagenesis), and the third for imaging-related terms (i.g. tomography).

11 Study records

11.1 Data management:

Each database will be screened individually by two groups of independent reviewers. The date of search strategy application will be registered. All the studies initially detected in the databases will be exported to EndNote Web (Thomson Reuters™, Toronto, Canada) as uniform combined files, such as .ris format. Duplicates will be removed using the software native automation tool. An additional manual removal of duplicates will be conducted manually in Microsoft Excel (Microsoft Corp.™, Redmond, USA). The remaining studies will be screened and selected following a three-step procedure.

11.2 Selection process:

The two groups of reviewers will be calibrated for the selection of studies based on the eligibility criteria. Once they are trained, the formal analysis of the full sample will start. The formal analysis inherent to the selection process will consider the following phases: I – Title reading: in which non-duplicate studies identified after the search will be read for more obvious exclusions; II – Abstract reading: the remaining studies will have their abstracts analyzed so the eligibility criteria can be applied in part, leading to more exclusions. Studies that did not have abstracts available were maintained for the next phase; III – Full text reading: in which the eligibility criteria can be fully applied. Exclusions performed in this phase will be registered separately with their respective justification. Steps I, II, and III will be performed independently by the two groups of reviewers, which will not be blind to the authorship, year of publication and any other aspect of the of study, supervised by a third participant (supervisor). The latter will help reach consensus in case of disagreements. After selecting studies based on their eligibility, the reference lists of the eligible studies will be screened for a final check of potential inclusions, followed by a consultation to an expert – so additional inclusions can be potentially suggested. If full texts are not available, they will be searched in ResearchGate™ (Berlin, Germany), followed by one tentative e-mail to the corresponding author (awaiting 7 days) and a subsequent request to the interlibrary COMUT network (Bibliographic Commutation Program).

11.3 Data collection process:

Piloting Microsoft Excel (Microsoft Corp.™, Redmond, USA) forms will be used for data collection. This process will take place pairwise by the groups of

reviewers, but independently. Data will be extracted in full for each study, separately. Only after the full text is read, screened for the information of interest and transcribed to the piloting forms, will the next study be assessed. The third reviewer will revise all the filled forms to guarantee quality control of the data collection process.

12 Data items

Data items to be considered will be initially the authorship, year of study's publication, country of origin, title of the manuscript, journal of publication and the most recent journal's ranking (from Q1 to Q4) according to Scimago (<https://www.scimagojr.com/>). Next, the sex and the age of the individuals will be recorded, type of medical imaging, radiographic equipment, the image acquisition protocol, patient's complaints, and the presence of systemic condition or physical alterations.

13 Outcomes

The outcomes will be the case-specific characteristics of each reported individual within the case reports and case series about the presence of panagenesis of the paranasal sinuses detected through medical imaging.

14 Risk of bias in individual studies

The risk of bias will be assessed based on the quality of each eligible study using the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) critical appraisal tool for observational descriptive studies namely case reports [18]. Each study will be classified according to the percentage of positive answers to the questions of the JBI tool. A high risk of bias will be registered when the study answered positively up to 49% of the questions, a moderate risk of bias will be between 50 and 69% of positive answers, and a low risk of bias will be positive answers above 70% [19]. Questions that answered as uncertain or not applicable (n/a) will not be counted for the calculation of the relative values (%) of positive answers. This process will be conducted independently by the two groups of reviewers with the supervision of the third reviewer for final decisions

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15 Data synthesis

Data will be treated by means of qualitative analysis, including narrative and descriptive synthesis of the case reports.

Traceable

Document
